

Legitimate questions on “Real-World Immunogenicity and Reactogenicity of Two Doses of Pfizer-BioNTech COVID-19 Vaccination in Children Aged 5-11 Years”

Manuel Graña^{1,2,*}

¹ Department of Computer Science and Artificial Intelligence, University of the Basque Country (UPV/EHU), Paseo Manuel de Lardizabal, 1, 20018 Donostia-San Sebastian, Spain;

² Computational Intelligence Group, University of the Basque Country (UPV/EHU), Spain;

* Correspondence: manuel.grana@ehu.eus; M.G.

Abstract: This paper poses some legitimate questions on the contents of a paper dealing with the issue of children vaccination against COVID-19 with the Pfizer-BioNTech COVID-19 Vaccination product. As a result of the huge number of publications raised by the COVID-19 pandemic, it is becoming urgently needed to make a clear distinction between scientific and marketing communication. The questions posed may help the reader to clarify the actual contribution and nature of the referred study. This paper does not follow the conventional structure of a scientific paper. For instance, we do not give specific conclusions, because we do not know in advance the potential answers to the posed questions. However, we expect that future readers of the referred paper may benefit from a critical reading using this paper to draw their own conclusions and to take it as a starting point for further enquiries.

Keywords: Legitimate Questions

1. Introduction

Posing legitimate questions is the cornerstone of knowledge generation, specifically critical for scientific development. Specifically, the scientific community must be free to attack and confirm or falsify scientific statements [1]. The COVID-19 pandemic has been characterized by the denial of such simple rights. The denial of the right to question is often grounded by the authorities on the obligation to trust without question. It is paradoxical that the public is forced into trusting corporations whose only liability is regarding the profit of the stakeholders. Specifically, in the USA, under the National Childhood Vaccine Injury Act of 1986 (42 U.S.C. §§ 300aa-1 to 300aa-34)¹ companies manufacturing products under the label of vaccines are not liable and can not be brought to court for lack of effectivity or serious adverse effects (SAE). All responsibility lies on the government institutions that must guarantee the public safety. Moreover, in Europe, the contract² for the purchase of Pfizer-Biontech *successful vaccines* deviates all liabilities to the Member States that are responsible for the administration of the doses purchased by the European Commission. The same institutions that survey the vaccine products safety are liable for any damage caused by them. The public is forced into automatic compulsory trust on companies that work for profit and on Member State institutions that might well be protecting them (the companies) in order to protect themselves to answer for lack of effectivity or SAEs.

Therefore, we assert our right to pose legitimate questions and to receive clarifying responses, ... or silence (that is better than wild dogs barking at the moon).

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¹ <https://www.congress.gov/bill/99th-congress/house-bill/5546>

² published by the Italian RAI https://www.rai.it/dl/doc/2021/04/17/1618676600910_APA%20BioNTech%20Pfizer__.pdf

33 This paper follows an unusual structure. We focus on a succession of aspects of
34 the paper [2], discussing each one and stating specific questions that we find relevant
35 in order to achieve a correct understanding of the study and its results, as well as of its
36 implications in the formation of public policies that the authorities claim to be sustained
37 by Science, despite contradicting evidences. For each aspect we pose specific questions

38 2. Conflicts of interest

39 The authors [2] declare no conflict of interests and no funding to carry out the
40 research. However, it is immediate to find in an internet search that the Sheba Medical
41 Center has been a showcase for Pfizer at several stages of the COVID-19 pandemic.
42 Recently, it has been publicized by the institution itself that it was the single site outside
43 USA running the observational studies on the immunogenicity of combined Omicron
44 boosters, and studies relating the relative immunogenicity of the Moderna and Pfizer
45 products as second boosters. It is difficult to understand that these works would have
46 been done for free when the Sheba Medical Center is a private for profit company and
47 Pfizer has huge financial interest in the outcome of the observational studies. It would
48 be highly clarifying to know if there is any kind of institutional contract or agreement
49 between the Sheba Medical Center and Pfizer, under whose umbrella the employees
50 of the Sheba Medical Center may be compelled to participate or carry out the study. It
51 would be of special interest to know if the potential agreement includes professional
52 help to write and publish the article, something that would ease the burden from the
53 already overwhelmed authors. Specifically, it would be quite clarifying to assess to what
54 extent the recruitment process has been true to the Helsinki declaration to know if the
55 refusal by parents to participate in the study would somehow conflict with any standing
56 agreement between the Sheba Medical Center and Pfizer. It would be enlightening to
57 know the actual number of employees with children in the target age range, and the
58 relative success of the call to participate, as well as the actual message conveyed for
59 recruitment. The conflicts of interest of reviewers and editors should also be stated when
60 an approved paper is to be used in the marketing strategy of a company. To summarize,
61 we pose the following legitimate questions on potential for conflicts of interest:

- 62 • Is there any framework contract between Sheba Medical Center and Pfizer that
63 covers the work reported in [2].? Are the costs of the study covered exclusively by
64 the authors?
- 65 • Could the Sheba Medical Center employees be/feel compelled or coerced into
66 participating in the study either as researchers or parents.?
- 67 • Have significant parts of the paper been written by professional writers hired by
68 Pfizer, Biontech, or the Sheba Medical Center ?
- 69 • Have the reviewers and paper editors any undeclared conflicts of interest?

70 3. Early bird infections after vaccinations

71 The first paragraph of Section 3 [2] includes the statement “Of them, 10 children
72 were found positive between day 0 and day 21 and were excluded from the analysis.”
73 This exclusion has not been stated in section 2.2 of the paper. Besides, the Table 1 has no
74 mention of the 10 children excluded from the study because they tested positive in the
75 period 0 to 21 days. Exclusion of these patients is noted as casual and irrelevant for the
76 main analysis. However, we note that 93 infections out of 120 recruited children is quite
77 close to 78% of infections in a vaccinated population. We think that some question about
78 vaccine efficacy can be posed even if the study was not designed to measure efficacy.

79 A well known but poorly understood phenomenon is the Antibody-dependent
80 enhancement (ADE) of virus infection and disease [3], which has been warned against for
81 COVID-19 vaccines [4]. A legitimate question is whether ADE is mechanism responsible
82 for these early infections after vaccination, which amount to almost 10% of the original
83 cohort. We have not found any effort by manufacturing companies and vaccination
84 advocates to check out this hypothesis by clinical or biochemical analysis, only plain

Figure 1. Graphical Relation between vaccination efforts and COVID cases and deaths. Extracted from <https://ourworldindata.org/explorers/coronavirus-data-explorer>.

85 denial of the evidence by simply dropping the data out of any study, like the authors do
86 in this paper.

87 To shed some light on the issue, we would like to put into consideration the relation
88 between vaccination efforts, COVID-19 cases and deaths in Israel visualized in Figure
89 1. The data has been downloaded from ourworldindata.org. The data and the matlab
90 code is available at zenodo.org [5]. Figure 1(a) plots together the vaccination doses and
91 the detected cases, both time series normalized in the [0,1] interval. The exponential
92 explosion of cases of the Omicron wave in early 2022 diminishes the scale of previous
93 waves of cases. To enhance the visualization of previous waves, we have plotted in
94 Figure 1(b) the normalized time series of doses and cases until the end of year 2021.
95 The correlation of doses and cases at the rising of the waves previous to Omicron is
96 now evident. the Israel reporting of testing efforts in ourworldindata.org stopped in
97 June 2022, at the time the number of tests per case was in the order of 5, conversely the
98 share of positive tests was over 30%. These two values can be interpreted as an endemic
99 situation of the COVID-19 after a massive intervention that achieved fully vaccination
100 of 65% of the population, as reported in ourworldindata.org. Therefore, the end of the
101 Omicron wave appears to be due to the end of massive testing efforts, rather than the
102 end of the endemic propagation of the virus.

103 In Figure 1(a) it can be appreciated that each wave of vaccination effort correlates
104 to or anticipates a wave of cases. In order to highlight this correlation/anticipation, we
105 plot the logarithms of cases and doses in Figure 1(c), where a nice correlation can be
106 observed in two periods (1) since the beginning of vaccination until the end of 2021,
107 and (2) after March 2022 until the end of the series. In the middle of these two periods,
108 there is a wave of doses at the end of 2021 that anticipates the Omicron wave of cases.
109 A time series causal analysis, i.e. applying Granger causality test, should conclude the
110 causal connection between doses and cases in this time period. Finally, Figure 1(d) plots
111 together the COVID-19 deaths and doses. During the year 2021 there is a nice correlation
112 between doses and deaths. Again, the wave of booster doses at the end of 2021 may
113 have a causal relation to the greatest COVID-19 mortality peak in Israel attributed to
114 the Omicron wave. Detailed quantitative analysis (using Granger causality tests or time
115 series coherence measures) should confirm and extend these qualitative observations.

116 These observations may point out to the fact that the early bird infections after
117 vaccination may not be a casual isolated event. Consequently, we believe that the
118 following are legitimate questions:

- 119 • Why have been removed the early bird infections from the reported results?
- 120 • Could early bird infections be a rather generalized epidemiological response that
121 explains the observed correlation of treatment waves and deaths and cases?
- 122 • Could early bird infections be due to ADE effects?
- 123 • In view of how the wave of doses at the end of year 2021 appears to antici-
124 pate/predict the surge of cases and deaths in early 2022, could ADE explain the
125 success of the Omicron variant?
- 126 • In several parts of the manuscript, authors refer to the “high immune scape” of
127 Omicron VOCs, as well as their high transmissibility in a strongly vaccinated
128 population. Have the authors considered that instead of “escaping the vaccine”
129 Omicron may have been boosted by the vaccine?
- 130 • What could be the public health impact of a massive pharmacological intervention
131 based on the same technology used to develop the COVID-19 vaccines to treat the
132 AIDS pandemic, i.e. to attack the HIV virus?

133 4. Efficacy

134 Authors of [2] acknowledge that the study was not designed to measure efficacy
135 of the treatment, however their definition of efficacy remains hidden and blurry. In
136 the abstract, we find the following phrase “Of the 110 vaccinated children, 75.5% were
137 infected, with only mild COVID-19 infection symptoms.” This phrase is constructed in a

138 way that suggests that the vaccination is the cause of the mild symptoms. However, in
139 the discussion section authors recall that during the worst of the Omicron wave, the risk
140 of moderate/severe/critical hospitalization for children was $3.2/10^5$ without referring
141 comorbidities that may be explanatory of the outcome and in absence of information
142 about vaccination status³. This fact does not support the suggested association between
143 vaccination and mild symptoms. Moreover, 37% of children in the age range of the study
144 were infected during the Omicron wave while the rate of infections in this study is over
145 75% in vaccinated children. We can formulate the following legitimate question:

- 146 • Is it possible to assert the efficacy of the vaccine in reducing the number of infections
147 when the ratio between infections in the vaccinated sample and in the (most likely
148 unvaccinated) population in the same age range is 2.04? I.e. the risk of infection in
149 vaccinated children appears to be twice to the general (unvaccinated) population.

150 In the discussion section [2], authors refer to the safety and efficacy study for children
151 in the age range 5-11 years carried out in the USA by Pfizer and Biontech [6]. This
152 study reports a relative efficacy of 90% of the vaccine (infection ratios 16/736 for placebo
153 and 3/1450 for vaccinated). However, in the vaccinated population infections in the
154 period between the first dose and seven days after the second dose went unrecorded and
155 unreported. This information was missing even in the supplementary material. Notice
156 that in [6] the count of infections for the placebo cohort starts the same day of the first
157 dose. Let us consider that the same ratio of infections observed in [2] (10 out of 120) in
158 the period between the first and second dose happened in [6]. This would amount to
159 120 infections that went unreported in [6], so the corrected relative risk increase **due to**
160 **taking** the vaccine would be 290% (almost a 3 fold increase in risk for the vaccinated),
161 conversely relative risk reduction achieved by **not** taking the vaccine would be 74%.
162 These results are so different to the desired conclusions that hiding the data should
163 have appear the only natural course of action to the people in charge of [6]. It becomes
164 self-evident that the data should be public and available to independent researchers
165 when the decision about an intervention over a sensitive population is based on the data
166 analysis results.

167 5. Poor adherence

168 Table 1 [2] gives some details of the adherence to the study by the children/parents.
169 The number of tested children at day 180 is a mere 26% of the original cohort of 110.
170 There is no specification of how many infected vs. uninfected children assisted to the
171 testing sampling in days 90 and 180.

- 172 • Is the lack of adherence to the study related to the emergence of infections?

173 Another surprising data in Table 1 is the increasing adherence to fill the questionnaires
174 that reach 100% in the two last visits. We can assume that they are online responses and
175 that the participants were actively encouraged to respond, but there is no explanation in
176 the paper.

177 6. Immunogenicity, natural immunity, and infections.

178 In Section 3.1 and supplementary tables S3 and S4 the summary results regarding
179 immunogenicity are reported. A salient fact is that, despite increase in immunogenicity
180 markers, 75.5% of the children were infected. This raises the following questions:

- 181 • How relevant are the immunogenicity markers to measure protection against infec-
182 tion, when their positive increase is uncorrelated with the actual infections?
- 183 • Are immunogenicity marker processes and instruments so tightly calibrated to the
184 ancestral Wuhan virus that they are useless to predict protection against even minor
185 variants?

³ It is not clear if vaccination was recommended in this period of time for children in the age range of the study, thus the vaccination status is very likely negative for most or all of these children.

- 186 • Taking into account that the ancestral Wuhan virus is no longer in circulation
187 (unless there is some redistribution of it into the general population from laboratory
188 samples), is it reasonable to think that the generation of specific antibodies for the
189 ancestral Wuhan virus may have no impact on the protection against new variants?

190 Another salient fact is that the increase in immunogenicity markers is greater, and
191 sustained longer, in infected children than in uninfected children. The difference is not
192 statistically significant at visit 3 (day 90) but it becomes significant at visit 4 (day 180).
193 Note that the log scale in figure 1 of [2] does hinder the visual observation of this fact. If
194 we deny natural immunity, then we deny that vaccines may work in any form. Given
195 that children's infections are usually short lived, (two weeks appear to be considered as
196 long covid by the authors), it is remarkable that the effects extend until day 180 into the
197 study. This observation raises the following question:

- 198 • Is natural immunity acquired by infection with the Omicron variant boosting the
199 immunogenicity markers of vaccinated children, even when these immunogenicity
200 markers are sharply focused on the the ancestral Wuhan virus?

201 The question is relevant, because the phenomenon goes in the opposite direction of
202 the recommendations of health authorities in most countries, that state that having a
203 dose after a natural infection "would increase the protection against new variants". The
204 immunogenicity results in [2] can be interpreted as "having an infection after vaccination,
205 your natural immunity will boost the protection against the ancestral Wuhan virus
206 intended by the vaccine". Of course, infection will protect you against the last variant,
207 otherwise no vaccine will be effective in any way. This leads to the following question:

- 208 • Is there any scientific (independent of financial interests) reason to impede children
209 to acquire natural immunity via natural infection with the latest variants that are in
210 circulation.?

211 Authors recall in the discussion section [2] that, despite the extremely high incidence of
212 Omicron in early 2022 (over 37% of children in the age range of the study), the risk of
213 moderate/severe/critical hospitalization was $3.2/10^5$ without referring comorbidities
214 that may be explanatory of the outcome. It is not unreasonable to think that the risk
215 from natural COVID-19 infection for **healthily developed children** is some orders of
216 magnitude lower than this figure. Hence, the above question can be reshaped as follows:

- 217 • Is the risk from the vaccination significantly greater or lower than the risk from
218 natural COVID-19 infection.?

219 In other words, for a population that has no adverse outcome from natural infection (i.e.
220 children), measuring the reduction in the number of infections by the vaccine should
221 be irrelevant for the establishment of a vaccination mandate or for personal decision.
222 Moreover, it has been publicly stated by Pfizer representatives that the clinical trials
223 did not measure transmission, hence the "do it to stop transmission" argument must
224 be put on hold until there is clear and sound proof that the products effectively stop
225 transmission. We can rephrase the above question as follows:

- 226 • Is the vaccine safer than natural infection.?

227 Recently there is a wave of publication that try to show that "yes, (some) vaccine is safer
228 than natural infection" in some specific way. But the study under analysis [2] does not
229 provide convincing proof, first because there is no control unvaccinated population,
230 second because safety signals that are evident from the data (to be discussed in the next
231 Section) are ignored by the authors in the conclusions and discussion.

232 Finally, in Section 2.2 [2], an exclusion criteria that authors have considered is
233 "history of SARS-CoV-2 in the previous 2 weeks". After noticing the long term effect of
234 natural infections on immunogenicity markers (increase after 180 days), it is reasonable to
235 expect some long term effects of previous infections. For instance, it would be interesting
236 to know if the uninfected children had some history of previous infections that may
237 have protected them additionally.

- 238 • Why previous history of infections (before previous 2 weeks) has been neglected in
239 the study.?

240 7. Safety: Lymphadenopathy

241 Table 3 of [2] contains a summary of reported adverse events. Seven events of
242 Lymphadenopathy were reported, i.e. 6% of the vaccinated children suffered Lym-
243 phadenopathy symptoms. Duration of the events was short, three days after the first
244 dose, one day after the second dose. It is interesting to note that Lymphadenopathy is
245 absent in Table 4. The acknowledged ratio of Lymphadenopathy events for the Pfizer-
246 BioNTech COVID-19 vaccine is 0.3% [7]. Moreover, it is considered as a serious adverse
247 event. The American CDC acknowledges an incidence of 0.9% in the range of age of the
248 study [8]. A recent case report on the accelerated progression of a specific lymphoma
249 which acknowledges a causality link with the BNT162b2 mRNA vaccine booster shot
250 [9] should be a strong note of caution about the unknown effects of the vaccine on the
251 lymphatic system. The specific question raised by these observations is the following:

- 252 • Why an observation of 6% incidence of lymphadenopathy (versus 0.3% or 0.9% in
253 other literature sources) does not raise a safety signal.?

254 The study in [2] is short lived and can not give information about these risks. The study
255 in [6] comments on a two year follow up, in an imprecise protocol.

- 256 • Why the manufacturing companies have not established a proactive long term
257 screening of the health status of the participants.?
258 • If the companies are having profits in the order of billions, why they can not spare
259 some money for a thorough follow up of study participants?
260 • Moreover, why this caution is not extended to the entire population that has been
261 treated with an experimental product?

262 8. Open science: open access data and code

263 There is a new policy in Europe regarding the accessibility of scientific instruments
264 enabling third parties to check, reproduce and falsify the published claims, that goes
265 under the name of Open Science⁴. It includes new resources for open access paper
266 publishing, but also resources to publish data and code that allows reproducibility and
267 falsifiability. In fact, all material related to this paper is being published in a zenodo entry
268 [5], including data, code, referred documents and papers, and the paper itself. Following
269 this philosophy, any claim that is not supported by Open Science best practices must be
270 considered inconclusive and speculative. Moreover, if the paper is intended to influence
271 public policies, then lack of Open Science standards should put the paper conclusions
272 on hold. Sometimes, papers refer to a public repository that is empty in order to give the
273 impression of sharing data and code [10]. The paper [2] gives no access link to the data
274 (which could have been easily anonymized) nor the code. There is not a single reference
275 of which software tools were used for the analysis in [2].

276 9. Conclusions

277 In its influential book [11] Edward Barnay set the basics for the control of the masses
278 via propaganda techniques, mostly with commercial and financial goals in mind. One of
279 the keystones of the propaganda machine is the use of well known and well respected
280 persons to promote the product. Of special interest are scientists which can endorse the
281 product with scientific like reasoning. This strategy has been and is being exploited by
282 the tobacco industry and the ultra-processed food and sugar industries [12–21]. In this
283 context, it is important for the reader to discriminate marketing papers from scientific
284 papers, specially when the papers are trying to influence public policies or set mandates.

⁴ https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/our-digital-future/open-science_en

285 Here we have revised and posed legitimate questions raised by the paper [2] with
286 the aim of clarifying its contents and contribution to the improved understanding of
287 the effects of the massive vaccination campaign. Israel is a very special case, because
288 it was selected as a case study for the Pfizer-Biontech product, so that its specific effect
289 can be assessed without confusion with other products. As such, it has produced a great
290 quantity of high quality epidemiological and clinical data that should be exploited to
291 start searching for the answers to the questions posed here and elsewhere.

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